

Maximum Parsimony Inference of Phylogenetic Networks in the Presence of Polyploid Complexes

Supplementary Material

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- Gene tree estimation error on the simulated data sets is shown in Figure S1.
- Comparison results between MPAllopp with and without subgenome assignment in terms of inference accuracy and running time are shown in Figures S2 and S3
- Estimated gene trees for the *Pachycladon* data are shown in Figure S4.
- Reconstructed phylogenetic networks of New Zealand *Pachycladon* are shown in Figure S5.

S1 Estimating phylogenies where the subgenome assignment is unknown

Figure S1: **Gene tree estimation error.** a) The rooted RF distance between the true gene trees and gene trees estimated by IQ-TREE on the 1/3/10/100 gene data sets. b) The rooted RF distance between true gene trees and maximum clade credibility gene trees derived from AlloppNET on the 1/3/10 gene data sets. Results are shown for gene trees excluding the outgroup. Red diamonds are means for ten replicates.

Figure S2: Scatter plots comparing the network estimation error difference between MPAllopp* and MPAllopp on simulated data over 10 replicates. The species network error was measured by the distance between true and estimated networks according to the metric of Nakhleh (2010). A positive value indicates that MPAllopp* yielded higher error than MPAllopp and vice versa for negative values. Here low, moderate and high ILS refer to mutation rates of 4×10^{-9} , 2×10^{-8} and 1×10^{-7} , respectively.

Figure S3: Scatter plots comparing running time (in CPU minutes) difference between MPAllopp* and MPAllopp on simulated data over 10 replicates. A positive value indicates that MPAllopp* required longer runtime than MPAllopp to complete the inference and vice versa for negative values. Here low, moderate and high ILS refer to mutation rates of 4×10^{-9} , 2×10^{-8} and 1×10^{-7} , respectively.

Figure S4: Maximum clade credibility gene trees of the *Pachycladon* data set. Gene names are abbreviated as follows: *CHS*, chalcone synthase; *CAD5*, cinnamyl alcohol dehydrogenase 5; *MS*, malate synthase; *PRK*, phosphoribulokinase; *MtN21*, MtN21 nodulation gene.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure S5: **Results on *Pachycladon*.** Species network reconstructed from the 10-taxon *Pachycladon* data set with five genes from Joly et al. (2009).

References

- Joly, S., P. B. Heenan, and P. J. Lockhart. 2009. A pleistocene inter-tribal allopolyploidization event precedes the species radiation of pachycladon (brassicaceae) in new zealand. *Molecular phylogenetics and evolution* 51:365–372.
- Nakhleh, L. 2010. A metric on the space of reduced phylogenetic networks. *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Computational Biology and Bioinformatics (TCBB)* 7:218–222.